

ORGANIZING "TECHNOLOGY" LESSONS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *The article describes the possibility of students to develop modern thinking and creativity skills, to demonstrate these skills, to work with technological documents, and to complete educational production tasks through TRIZ-method, which is one of the interactive methods.*

Keywords: *TRIZ-method, technology, polymers, training process, technological document, modern methods of teaching.*

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of April 6, 2017 "On approval of the state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education" No. 187, approved by the State educational standard aimed at the formation of competencies in students in the subject "Technology" and the 2017 of the Ministry of Public Education "Technology" for grades 5-7 based on the curriculum of "Technology" approved by order No. 190 of June 3, "On the approval and implementation of improved curricula based on the requirements of state educational standards of general secondary education" Technology of processing polymer materials", "Fundamentals of economic science" sections and topics related to sections are included. Preparation of students for productive work in the future, setting up work to direct them to acquire the professions they are interested in is mainly the responsibility of the subject of labor education in general education schools. Instilling in students love for knowledge and work, respect for workers, educating them in the spirit of community, loyalty to the country, friendship, mutual respect is the educational feature of technology science and vocational education. To implement the educational tasks of technology and vocational education, it is effective to use the content of teaching, as well as organizational forms and methods of educational work. The condition of transition to each stage of development is not only regular increase of labor productivity and creation of abundance of material goods, but also education of high moral qualities in the young generation. It is formed primarily in the process of public interest. In the process of technology training, pupils are educated to take care of the equipment in the workshop, to use raw materials economically. Work culture in educational workshops, organization of the workplace and proper planning of training and work activities; In addition to hand tools, the use of various devices in technology and vocational education classes is of great importance, because they not only improve the quality of work of students, but also increase labor productivity. The teacher's personal example during demonstration of labor and craft methods is considered a powerful educational tool for students. In the process of practical training in technological science and vocational education, the goals and tasks of labor and vocational education are implemented while revealing the content of the subject. Therefore, practical training should be understood as the organization of educational and work activities that include both team and individual work, carried out under the guidance of a technology teacher in order to actively, consciously and firmly master the educational material. Nowadays, it is necessary to organize the educational process in different ways in order to form students as well-rounded individuals. Because it allows the student to search for answers to the questions he is interested in through the Internet. However, the student

understands the meaning of this activity only if he acquires knowledge, skills and abilities through academic subjects. The number of innovative technologies and interactive methods in education has increased greatly. The TRIZ method that we recommend has its own characteristics.

TRIZ (IMRN in Uzbek) is a science that develops the general laws of artificial systems, that is, it means the theory of development of creative problems (IMRN). The author of this theory is G.S. Altshuller, and the main object of analysis of TRIZ is artificial systems. Concepts such as creative approach and creative thinking are included in the TRIZ method. TRIZ is a method of developing creative issues.

TRIZ is knowledge in the field of the theory of creative problem solving and mechanisms of technical development. The purpose of using this method is to use the technology of developing the student's creativity, i.e. creative thinking. As an example, we offer lesson technology on the topic of the 6th grade program. It should be noted that many methods of general didactic nature are used in the process of technology science. However, such methods as practical demonstration of work methods, exercises related to their implementation, working with technical references and technological documents, and performance of educational production tasks are methods specific to the science of «Technology».

It is possible to organize training using many types of pedagogical technology in technology classes. Pedagogical technology is aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's curiosity. According to A. Kushner, methodology is a way of popularizing best practice or inventing a new way of imparting knowledge, and the result cannot always be guaranteed. And technology is a process that produces a predetermined result under any circumstances. The science of technology is connected with the tools, methods and forms of pedagogical technology. Pedagogical technology in the course of the lesson ensures the training of personnel at the level of the requirements of the state educational standards in the conditions of mass education. Our ultimate goal is to deliver independent-minded, creative, inquisitive and talented youth for the future.

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